

significant difference in their level of input use, except for the size of land cultivated, where female farmers worked on a much smaller area. This has significant implications in terms of efficiency. Because of their inability to expand farm area due to restrictive policies on land ownership and the tenure system, female farmers were forced to cultivate the same area every year, thereby depleting soil fertility and affecting output.

The results of the stochastic production frontier model validated this observation. The production function estimate indicated that one of the critical inputs to the attainment of high yield was land input. The estimated coefficient of farm size was 0.31 and it was very significant (Table 2). The other critical inputs that were significant were labor and agrochemical inputs. But, for the other inputs, the level of use was almost the same for male and female farmers.

Table 2. Regression results of the stochastic frontier and socioeconomic model.^a

Variable	Coefficient	Standard error	t ratio
<i>Stochastic frontier model</i>			
Constant	2.31	0.22	10.66**
Farm size	0.31	0.57	5.34**
Family labor	1.00	0.009	1,114.82**
Hired labor	0.14	0.03	4.19**
Traction	0.03	0.05	0.61
Agrochemicals	0.14	0.05	2.67**
Seed	-0.004	0.009	-0.41
Fertilizer	0.004	0.006	0.60
d ² =du/dv	1.33	0.21	6.28**
<i>Socioeconomic model</i>			
Constant	0.38	0.18	2.14**
Age	0.02	0.01	4.27**
Education	0.01	0.01	0.30
Contact with extension agent	0.01	0.01	1.54
Farm income	5.89	5.93	0.99
Farming experience	-0.01	0.01	-1.12
Household size	-0.01	0.01	-0.13
Sex	-0.28	0.09	3.11**

^aLog likelihood function = -616.83.

The technical inefficiency portion of the model indeed showed that male farmers were more technically efficient than female farmers. The sex variable had a negative coefficient and

was significant. The only other significant coefficient was age, which indicates that the older the farmer, the more inefficient he or she is.

Comparative analysis of costs incurred by seed growers and nonseed growers

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The annual rice seed requirement of Sri Lanka approximates 1 million t. The state farms were unsuccessful in supplying the required amount in the past for various reasons. Hence, the government inter-vened to expand production of certified seed by private growers. However, this approach has certain limitations: difficulty in

maintaining the standards, marketing problems, and not-so-established differences in cost of production. This study aimed to identify differences in production cost between seed growers and nonseed growers.

The study was carried out in Hambantota, a major rice-growing district. Forty-two private seed producers were

chosen as respondents. The same number of growers was randomly selected from five agricultural service centers (Yodhakandiya, Lunawa, Weeraketiya, Netolpitiya, and Meegahajadura). Cultivation cost for the 2001-02 maha season was obtained employing pretested questionnaires (see table).

Seed producers entailed extra expenses removing off-types and for drying, winnowing, and processing to maintain high quality standards. The results demonstrate that the difference in production cost was not significant, though seed producers reported a slightly higher figure. The seed producers obtained a higher average yield. Certified seeds were sold at the farm-gate price of Rs 17.75 kg⁻¹ in contrast to the normal Rs 15.12 kg⁻¹. In fact, seed growers received an extra profit margin of Rs 29,420 ha⁻¹ season⁻¹. This will result in an extra net income of Rs 4,900 ha⁻¹ month⁻¹, which is hardly insufficient to promote the seed-growing industry. Moreover, many farmers cultivated small plots (<0.5 ha) and some were sharecroppers who had to leave 1/3 of the harvest as land rent.

Differences in cost of production.^a

Item	Seed growers (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Percent of cost component	Nonseed growers (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Percent of cost component
Seed	3,583	6.6	3,812	6.6
Land preparation and plant establishment	11,680	19.7	11,794	20.5
Fertilizer application	5,590	9.4	5,504	9.5
Weed, pest, and disease control	4,544	7.6	5,209	9.0
Tenancy and lease arrangements	10,313	17.4	10,275	17.8
Special activities for seed production	2,095	3.5	Not applicable	0
Registration	1,000	1.6	Not applicable	0
Av cost (Rs ha ⁻¹)	59,196		57,479	0
Av yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	7,177		6,366	
Av price (Rs)	17.75		15.12	
Gross returns (Rs)	127,392		96,253	
Profit (Rs ha ⁻¹)	68,196		38,775	

^aUS\$1 = Rs 98.

Hence, seed growers do not receive even the above-mentioned real income. The price received for certified seed was rather low. Further, seed farmers encountered marketing problems

at the beginning of the season. This has become a common problem, necessitating policies to buy rice seed above Rs 20 kg⁻¹.

